

Research Article**Exploration of the Gap between Perceptions and Practices of L.S.R.W skills in English Language Teaching in Selected Engineering Colleges: Implication and Remedial Measures****M. Surendra Reddy**

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Abstract

The role of LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing) Skills is understandably central to effective language learning in any stream of higher education. The issue becomes doubly crucial in Teaching and Learning of English Language to students of Engineering as a good number of Engineering Graduates are found to be lacking in communication skills. While classroom practices, generally it is found that a mismatch between these perceptions and teachers and learners often recognize the importance of balancing the skills development, actual implementation of the LSRW Skills. Hence the present paper explores the gap between teachers' and students' perceptions of LSRW skills, and the real class-room practices thereof. Using surveys, classroom observations and by contacting the students directly, this study identifies important factors for the gap concerned and measures to be taken up for bridging this gap. The findings of the study widely suggest the need for pedagogical reforms and skills-based integrated instruction.

Keywords: LSRW skills, perception, practices , communicative competence, language, Pedagogy, remedial measures.

1. Introduction:-

In the globalized world, importance of English language and proficiency in it has become a prerequisite for academic success and for professional Career, particularly for Engineering graduates. The mastery of four essential English language skills Listening. (LSRW) is essential for effective communication modern language teaching emphasizes communication Competence, for which all these four languages. Skills are integrated.

However, English Language Teaching in Engineering colleges often focuses on theoretical knowledge, rather than practical Communication Skills. In many educational institutions ELT has become as an exam- oriented and there exists a disparity between what teachers and students believe about LSRW skill and what is practicing in Indian engineering class-rooms. Many studies suggest that many students, particularly from rural and Vernacular background, facing problems with Communication despite of studying English. from kinds of Garden. This research paper highlights a critical mismatch between perceived importance not actual pedagogical practice.

2. Objectives of the study :-

1. To analyze Teachers' and students' perception of LSRW skills.

2. To examine classroom practices related to LSRW skills.
3. To identify the key factors, causing the gap between perception and practice.
4. To suggest some strategies for effective integration of LSRW skills.

3. Review of literature :

In ELT Contexts , LSRW skills are treated as an integrated approach rather than isolated competencies. Gurung et al. (2023) state that LSRW skills are central to English language acquisition and are strongly supported by educational policies like National Education Policy 2020.

Research in ELT consistently emphasizes that LSRW skills should be taught in an integrated manner. Sridevi (2024) in IER Journal argues that effective teaching requires combining multiple strategies to develop learners language competence.

Research in ELT highlights the importance of integration of all four language skills. Communicative language teaching (CLT) promotes real-life communication through balanced skill development. English Teachers' Needs analysis and Technology Integration from ELTAI, quoted that 'Lack of proper needs analysis and outdated teaching methods.

- **Identification of soft skills Gaps in Engineering Education:** quoted in ResearchGate suggests that Engineering student, often exhibit Soft skill deficiencies, including poor communication abilities which effect employability.
- Studies also emphasizes that LSRW skills can be improved through the process of continuous practice and with interaction, but not through passive instruction.

Teachers give priority for reading and writing due to current examination patterns.

1. Listening and speaking are often neglected.
2. There is a lack of authentic materials and training.
3. Due to this, students are having theoretical knowledge but poor in communication.

4. Methodology :-

This study is mostly based on survey method following quantitative, and partly also descriptive approach.

(A) Participants :-

1. 10 English language teachers.
2. Engineering students at selected engineering colleges in Rayalaseema region.

(B) Tools used :-

1. Questionnaires
2. Classroom observations and secondary data
3. Review of ELT research studies.
4. Analysis of classroom practices in engineering colleges.

5. Analysis:-

(A) Perceptions of LSRW skills :-

Teachers' perceptions

1. LSRW skills are essential for employability.
2. Communication skills are as important as technical skill.
3. Students must be trained in real - life communication.
4. Most of the teachers agree that all four skills are equally important.
5. Students express their interest in improving speaking skills.
6. Both groups are accepting the fact that the communication has a great value in English.

Students' perceptions

1. English proficiency is necessary for placements.
2. Speaking skills are considered most important.
3. Fear and lack of confidence hinder participation.

(B) Practices in Engineering Colleges :-

1. Traditional teaching methods like lecture – based method is followed.
2. Focusing mainly on grammar and written examinations.
3. Lack of practical exposure like minimal real – life communication practice.
4. Reading writing are dominating remaining to skills.
5. Speaking activities are limited as per curriculum needs.
6. Listening activities often practiced, due to lack of audio resources.
7. Assessment issues also found as the evaluation process is mainly focused on writing skills.

(C) Gap between Perceptions and Practice :-

The study identifies the following major gaps:

Perception	Practice
Importance of all four LSRW skills	Mainly focusing on writing skill only
Need for communication skills	Exam oriented approach of practice
Emphasis on practical learning	Theoretical instructions are mainly focusing

(D) Reasons for gap:

1. Examination oriented curriculum, rather than communication efficiency in language.
2. Time constraints, for every 6 months, syllabus is changing, due to semester system.
3. Lack of teacher training in communicative methods.
4. Large classroom size.
5. Teachers' domination is more in classroom interaction but limited student participation.
6. Most of the students are from rural areas, mother tongue influence is more on speaking English.

(E) Implication for teaching :-

To bridge the gap the following measures are Suggested.

1. Integrate all four skills in lesson planning, before going to teach a lesson.
2. Conduction of Role plays, Group discussions and debits.
3. Incorporate technology (audio, video, language apps).
4. Provide frequent teacher training as Inservice training program.
5. Modify assessment strategies to include speaking and listening.

(F) Remedial Measures:-

1. Focus on interaction and real – life communication.
2. Use of language labs, AI tools and multimedia.
3. Digital platforms for LSRW skill development.
4. Student participation must be encouraged.

6. Findings of the study :-

1. A significant gap exists between perception and practice.
2. Technology integration is insufficient.
3. Lack of students practical exposure.
4. Teaching methods are exam oriented.

7. Conclusion:

This study confirms a significant gap between perceptions and practices of LSRW skills in English language teaching in Indian class-rooms. while both teachers and students recognize the importance of all four skills, but having limits in their implementation. Bridging this gap requires a shift from traditional teaching methods to interactive, technology based and student

centric approaches. Addressing their gap requires coordinated efforts in curriculum design, teachers training and assessment reforms to promote holistic language learning. With these innovative methods and use of technology, engineering graduates can be equipped with the required communication skills that are necessary for global competitiveness.

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